

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MWANGI****FIRST NAME: AGNES****PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401****COURSE CODE : LLM****PERIOD NUMBER: P6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Direct quotations are used in the following circumstances except?

- The words are from an authority who backs up your views.
- The words are strikingly original.
- The quoted words constitute evidence which backups your reasons.
- The words contain a general point from a passage which you wish to use.¹**

2. Citation of sources is not required in which circumstance?

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, rev. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and the university of Chicago Press editorial staff, 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 32-33.

- When the information is common knowledge found in numerous sources.²**
- When you use major ideas from your writing support group.
- When the information is publicly available online free of charge.
- When you have paraphrased the source's words using your own words.
3. **Which of the following is not one of the main traits of effective writing?**
- Logical organization.
- Stimulating ideas.
- Writing regularly.³**
- Smooth reading sentences.
4. **Which of the following sentences is wrongly punctuated?**
- This dress costs \$ 35.70 every Tuesday.
- The following are different kinds of sporting activities, football, basketball, netball, hockey, and volleyball.
- It is estimated that in the next twenty years the human population will be 1000000000000.⁴**

² Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 51-52

³Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning* (Wilmington Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 20.

⁴ Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer, *Write Source 2000*, 388-91.

Most intelligent, well- educated students wish to become scientists.

5. **The following principles are applicable in paraphrasing except?**

The writing style used to paraphrase should be different from the author's writing style.

The language used should resemble the words of the author.⁵

The paraphrased information should be an accurate representation of the original words.

The paraphrased information should be properly cited.

6. **Which of the following is incorrect use of abbreviation in the American English system?**

Dear Mr. Kamau:

"She screamed, 'I did it' and then laughed out loudly."

'He shouted, "get out of here" and then closed the door.'⁶

"The lady sang a beautiful song."

7. **Which of the following is the proper way to write time under the British English system?**

⁵ Euclid University, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015), 24 accessed December 12, 2019, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/>.

⁶ Ibid., 59

- The lecture starts at 17.00pm.
- The show starts at 12.30pm and ends at 2pm.**⁷
- The closing date for the purchase of the tickets is 12 noon on 12 October.
- Dinner is served from 11.30am to 14:00.
8. **Which of the following uses the correct British English format for writing numerals?**
- He was the 1st one to arrive.
- She was fourteenth on the list.
- 25 per cent of the class are computer literate.
- She graduated with a first-class honor.**⁸
9. **Which of the following is the proper way of citing cases under the bluebook citation system?**
- Kamau Mutinda & Co. v. Njeri, Ltd.**⁹

⁷ Euclid University, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4* (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015), 105 accessed February 01, 2020, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-4/>

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ The Columbia Law Review Association, the Harvard Law Review Association, the University of Pennsylvania Law Review, and The Yale Law Journal, eds., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th ed (Cambridge: Harvard Law Review Association, 2010), 7-9.

- Kamau Mutinda, et al. v. Njeri, Ltd.
- Kamau Mutinda & Co plaintiff. v. Njeri, Ltd defendant.
- In the matter of Kamau Mutinda.

10. **The following are all approved styles of citation under the bluebook citation system except?**

- Charles Mwangi, Jr. & Jane Wanjiru, A Quest for Justice (2010).
- Charles Mwangi, Jr. with Jane Wanjiru, A Quest for Justice (2010).
- Charles Mwangi, III., & Jane Wanjiru, A Quest for Justice (2010).
- Prof. Charles Mwangi & Jane Wanjiru, A Quest for Justice (2010).¹⁰**

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015. Accessed February 01,2020. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-4/>

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Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*. Wilmington Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory

¹⁰ Ibid., 138-39.

Commented [GK1]: You forgot to italicize all the titles, this is critical and an essential part of reference writing

G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and the university of Chicago Press editorial staff. 8th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.